

SliceDroid: Towards Reconstructing Android Application I/O Behaviors from Kernel Traces

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Abstract—Live threat detection and forensic analysis are becoming increasingly important in the mobile device ecosystem. The analysis of kernel traces is the standard approach for performing such tasks on the desktop and in the cloud. A major factor limiting the effectiveness of such approaches in Android is the semantic gap between low-level kernel events and high-level behaviors, stemming from Android’s multilayer software stack. SLICEDROID is an efficient and transparent approach to reconstruct application behaviors based only on kernel traces. It builds on two key insights: a) necessary information can be traced transparently using existing mechanisms to inspect internal kernel structures, and b) I/O events can be attributed to the processes that initiated them by appropriately slicing the collected traces.

We implement a prototype of SLICEDROID and show that it is capable of reconstructing core application behaviors with good accuracy and minimal performance overhead. Furthermore, to showcase the immediate practical relevance of our approach, we perform case studies on a commercial spyware application, as well as on popular Google Play Store apps. Contrary to previous reports, we find that it is possible to reconstruct high-level application behaviors exclusively from kernel events efficiently and transparently, that is, without modifications to the kernel or the Android framework. This is achieved at the cost of a configurable decrease in precision. We offer an open-source implementation of SLICEDROID to promote further research and support improvements in auditing and forensic analysis tools.

I. INTRODUCTION

ANDROID in its many flavors is the most popular operating system in the world [1]. Its daily use by billions of people and the value of data and interfaces accessible through its apps and sensors make it a prime target for threat actors. As a result, Android users face an evolving landscape of threats including increasingly sophisticated malware [2]–[5], powerful spyware (such as Pegasus [6] and Predator [7]), supply-chain attacks [8], [9], and pre-installed system components that perform unwanted actions [10]–[12].

Most existing mitigations to those threats are based on *in-lab* analysis of applications to determine whether they perform unwanted actions—and can therefore be classified as malware. The analysis is either static (analyzing the source or bytecode of applications) [13]–[22] and/or dynamic (analyzing the runtime behavior of applications in a test environment) [23]–[31], recently also utilizing dedicated hardware features [32]. Although such approaches have greatly improved the security of the Android ecosystem, more is needed to combat sophisticated threats. For example, in-lab analysis can do little to protect users from attacks exploiting vulnerabilities in

the Android Framework, highly-evasive malware, misbehaving AI agents, malicious or curious system apps, or applications installed without the users’ knowledge (such as commercial spyware apps). To combat these threats, it is necessary to capture and analyze the actual execution behaviors of applications on *live* user devices. Existing approaches for dynamic malware analysis either require extensive instrumentation of applications and the OS, or incur significant tracing overhead, making them unsuitable for that purpose.

In the desktop and cloud ecosystems, so-called Provenance-based Intrusion Detection Systems have evolved greatly in recent years [33]–[37] to combat sophisticated threats. Such systems collect execution traces (usually system calls) from live devices that characterize the behaviors of different processes and apply different forms of reasoning (e.g. ML-based anomaly detection) to flag potentially malicious groups of processes, indicating attacks. Kernel tracing, e.g. via system calls, offers well-known critical advantages, as (a) it is harder to detect and evade compared to tracing in userspace, (b) the trusted computing base (TCB) is limited to the kernel, and (c) modern kernels like Linux offer efficient mechanisms to trace kernel events (auditd, tracepoints, kprobes). Unfortunately, such approaches cannot be directly transferred to Android mainly due to the *semantic gap* [38]–[40] between the OS kernel (Linux) and Android’s extensive userspace platform.

The semantic gap manifests itself in Android, as user processes rarely interact with the kernel themselves, but rather make extensive use of middleware helper daemons offered by Android’s extensive userspace (see Figure 1). The reconstruction of security-relevant high-level behaviors (e.g. read file, use camera, use microphone, read location) has been shown to be a difficult problem by Nisi et al. [40]. The underlying cause of this difficulty is showcased in the example of a camera request, as shown in Figure 1. The high-level behavior `Camera.TakePicture` expressed by the `Camera App` process does not result in any related system calls by the process itself (such as opening a camera device special file), apart from inter-process communication (IPC) ones. Instead, in this example, the kernel boundary is crossed by the `Camera Provider` process, which invokes the necessary system calls to communicate with the `Camera Driver` via Linux’s Virtual File System (VFS). Obviously, little information can be gained by capturing system calls of the `Camera App` process. An alternative approach would be to capture all the *contents* of the process’s IPC communication and analyze them to deduce the intended behavior,

Fig. 1. Simplified depiction of an Android camera request, showing the `Camera.TakePicture` behavior, achieved by passing information through six different system layers (L5–L0).

as proposed by Copperdroid [26]. Such an approach, while useful for in-lab analysis, has fundamental conceptual and practical limitations when considered for deployment in the wild, most importantly: (a) the amount of data to be captured is orders of magnitude greater than when capturing system call file path arguments, and (b) knowledge of userspace APIs is required, e.g. in the case of the camera request of Figure 1, the analyst would have to deduce the intended behavior by inspecting the commands sent by the `Camera App` process to the `Camera Server`—and in any case, the only thing deduced would be an *intended* behavior and not a behavior that *actually* took place, after e.g. app permissions were checked. In general, bridging the semantic gap by reconstructing high-level behaviors from low-level kernel events is an important and still unsolved problem that is especially challenging in the context of Android [32], [40]. Approaches that bridge this gap would enable behavioral analysis based on efficiently collected provenance data, with significant practical implications for real-time threat detection, forensics, and malware analysis (see Section VII).

Problem. In this paper we investigate the fundamental question of whether it is possible to reconstruct high-level behaviors of Android processes only from efficiently collected kernel traces. In the process, we introduce SLICEDROID.

Core idea. The core idea of SLICEDROID is simple: I/O behaviors can be reconstructed by linking: (a) IPC paths, i.e. communication paths between processes, and (b) accesses of specific device nodes (e.g. `/dev/camera` for the simplified example of Figure 1). By tracing suitable IPC and device-node related events performed by *all* processes on a running system and appropriately slicing them [41], we can attribute low-level events to the applications that initiated them. To showcase the validity of our idea, we instantiate it by tracing events from the VFS layer of the Linux kernel, as well as IPC ones

(UNIX sockets, binder¹), using the `ftrace` [42] framework included by default in modern Linux kernels, and by extension in Android. The general workflow of SLICEDROID is shown in Figure 2. After appropriately configuring the tracing framework ① and collecting system-wide traces ②, we partition them in overlapping windows and *slice* them by following IPC paths ③, thus identifying relevant events originating from processes of interest.

In the example of Figure 1, SLICEDROID is able to capture the in-kernel call to the `Camera Driver` and associate it all the way up to a request by the `Camera App` following IPC paths. SLICEDROID’s simple idea is deceptively powerful, as it can capture complex operations, like direct memory access and sharing of memory buffers, without explicitly tracing them; device-related calls are still needed to configure and synchronize memory accesses and file descriptors need to be passed by other forms of IPC between processes. The remaining notable challenge is how to map VFS events to actual I/O behaviors. To overcome this challenge, we extract the Linux device nodes of those events ④ and employ a data-driven approach to learn mappings between them and high-level behaviors. Finally, we use these mappings to reconstruct the actual high-level behaviors of an application ⑤. Overall, at a conceptual level, with SLICEDROID we show that contrary to previous approaches that relied on expensive tracing of communication *contents* to reconstruct I/O behaviors, it is possible to do so based on communication *metadata* (communication endpoints, direction, timing), drawing interesting comparisons with the effectiveness of traffic analysis in communication networks. We provide a more detailed placing of our work among existing approaches in Section II.

Contributions. We are the first, to the best of our knowledge, to show that it is possible to reconstruct Android application behaviors exclusively from kernel traces, at the cost of a configurable decrease in precision. In more detail:

- We identify and define the behavior reconstruction problem, only considered implicitly in prior work (Section IV-A).
- We introduce SLICEDROID, a simple approach using well-established concepts (slicing [41]) to produce a novel solution for the problem at hand (Section IV-B). We realize the approach on Android by tracing appropriate functions in the Linux kernel (Section IV-C).
- We perform experiments on more than 1 000 applications (Section V), along with case studies (Section VI), to showcase the effectiveness and practical utility of our techniques and highlight the involved tradeoffs.

Availability: A replication package for our evaluation results is available on [Zenodo](https://zenodo.org/). SLICEDROID is available on [Github](https://github.com/SliceDroidTeam/SliceDroid)².

II. RELATED WORK

The problem of behavior reconstruction has been studied in several domains.

¹<https://developer.android.com/reference/android/os/Binder>

²<https://github.com/SliceDroidTeam/SliceDroid>

Fig. 2. SLICEDROID end-to-end operation

Behavior reconstruction in Android. Copperdroid [26] is a characteristic example of an approach that reconstructs sensitive behaviors in Android by combining information from system calls and the *contents* of binder IPC. Dagger [43] on the other hand, constructs provenance graphs that include system calls and IPC information, and compares them to behavior graph patterns previously extracted from the internal working logic of the Android framework. Both approaches require detailed knowledge of the internals of the Android framework to map recorded events to predefined behaviors. Copperdroid uses Virtual Machine Introspection to extract traces, while Dagger uses `strace` and information from the `proc` and `sys` filesystems with a measured runtime overhead of less than 63%. Contrary to these approaches, SLICEDROID is lightweight and *agnostic* to the internals of the Android framework and thus can also capture behaviors of privileged system apps, being useful in discovering unwanted behaviors and bugs in the framework layer of the OS. There also exist other sophisticated approaches to extract behavior characteristics from multiple layers of the Android OS with extremely fine-grained granularity [29], [44], [45]. Understandably, such approaches incur overheads of 5x to 40x and are very useful for testing in the lab but unsuitable for deployment in the wild.

Another interesting line of work is information flow analysis through dynamic taint tracking. Approaches such as Taintdroid [27], TaintART [28], ARTist [46], and FSAFlow [25] generally offer fine-grained taint propagation information by instrumenting the Java runtime system of Android or the apps under test. In general, these approaches can be detected and evaded by malware as they operate in the same security boundary as the apps under test. Moreover, they incur a non-negligible overhead and require system modifications. Contrary to these approaches, we collect traces exclusively from the kernel, benefiting from its well-defined security boundary. ClearScope [47] is a sophisticated system that provides full system provenance for Android devices by integrating many of the approaches mentioned above. It has been shown to be effective in detecting malicious actions in several engagements performed in the context of DARPA’s Transparent Computing program.³ ClearScope involves extensive modifications to the kernel and Android Framework and on-line static instrumentation of third-party applications.

Nisi et al. [40] tackle the problem of behavior reconstruction

in its general form. Their goal was to reconstruct Android API method calls from an app’s system call sequences alone. They had limited success and concluded that doing this is more difficult than previously thought. SLICEDROID tackles this problem by following IPC communication to construct slices that capture communication with the kernel initiated by an app but performed deep in the Android framework. Nisi et al.’s data-driven approach inspired our experimental workflow (see Section V).

Behavior reconstruction in provenance systems. Provenance systems capture lightweight traces (usually system calls) in order to answer forensic questions or perform intrusion and APT detection, and thus implicitly perform behavior reconstruction. Research in this domain has intensified in recent years [34] with a number of systems [35], [36], [48] tailored for attack detection and investigation on multiple Windows or Linux hosts. The semantic gap prevalent in Android and other similar operating systems makes it difficult to include such hosts in the analysis. Our approach can help bridge the semantic gap and enable host-based detection approaches to find applicability in the mobile device ecosystem.

Built-in Android transparency mechanisms. Android 12 introduced visual privacy indicators⁴ for camera and microphone use by non-system apps, providing a degree of transparency to users. These indicators are generated by the framework by inspecting relevant API calls, and are displayed for a minimum of 5 seconds on the status bar. While useful, such measures do not cover system apps and can be circumvented in several ways, including abusing the permission system (as done by commercial spyware apps—see Section VI), overlay attacks [49], or exploiting bugs in the Android framework.⁵ Tracing behaviors in the kernel layer, as SLICEDROID does, mitigates these limitations.

Contribution beyond related work. Our approach is fundamentally different to prior work: we are able to reconstruct behaviors with high transparency and low tracing overhead without depending on the intermediate layers of the OS and their implementation details. Achieving this comes with a trade-off in *precision*, i.e. coarse-grained behaviors and the possibility of false positives, as will be discussed later.

Figure 3 shows conceptual trade-offs of existing behavior analysis approaches. *Transparency* is defined by Ning and

³<https://www.darpa.mil/research/programs/transparent-computing>

⁴<https://source.android.com/docs/core/permissions/privacy-indicators>

⁵<https://nvd.nist.gov/vuln/detail/CVE-2023-21083>

TABLE I

QUALITATIVE COMPARISON TO REPRESENTATIVE RELATED APPROACHES FOCUSING ON THEIR BEHAVIOR IDENTIFICATION COMPONENT. OVERHEAD FIGURES ARE TAKEN FROM THE RESPECTIVE PAPERS. *: OVERHEAD IS APPROXIMATED BY MEASUREMENTS ON STRACE [50].

Papers	Behavior Identification Approach	Domain	Scope	Efficiency	Precision	Transparency
TaintDroid [27]/TaintART [28]	Runtime Instrumentation	Malware	App	▶ (~ 1.2x)	●	○
FSAFlow [25]	App Instrumentation	Malware	App	● (~ 1x)	●	○
Copperdroid [26]	VMI – Binder buffer analysis	Malware	System	▶ (~ 2x)	●	○
Ninja [32]	Runtime Introspection	Malware	System	○ (~ 8x)	●	●
Malton [29]	API and app Instrumentation	Malware	System	○ (~ 25x)	●	○
Nisi et al. [40]	Strace and syscall pattern matching	General	App	▶ (~ 1–2x)*	○	▶
SLICEDROID (this paper)	Kernel tracing and slicing	General	System	● (~ 1x)	▶	●

Fig. 3. Tradeoffs of dynamic behavior analysis approaches

Zhang [32], [51] as three properties for the analysis environment: (a) it should be isolated, (b) it should exist in a bare-metal platform without any SW/HW modifications, and (c) it should not leak any detectable footprints. We define *precision* as the ability of the system to reconstruct behaviors with fine granularity and good accuracy. Although each tool proposed in the literature is uniquely positioned in the trade-off triangle due to various design and implementation choices, at a conceptual level, the basic methods of Introspection, Instrumentation, and Kernel tracing, can each satisfy at most two properties. Introspection, i.e. inspecting the memory of userspace processes at runtime, can achieve high transparency and precision but is inefficient (e.g. Ninja [32] incurs up to 154x overhead for API tracing). Instrumentation (e.g. TaintDroid [27]) can achieve high precision and efficiency but requires extensive modifications, leading to low transparency. This work investigates an understudied point in the design space, introducing an approach that achieves *efficiency* and *transparency* (kernel-userspace isolation, no system modifications), suitable for applications such as live threat detection, forensic analysis, and crowdsourcing [52]. In Table I we provide a qualitative comparison of SLICEDROID to seminal representative approaches in the related work mentioned earlier to highlight the involved tradeoffs. SLICEDROID is the first approach to achieve efficiency and transparency with a configurable tradeoff in precision.

III. BACKGROUND

Below we provide some necessary background information.

Android architecture Android is an Operating System (OS) based on the Linux kernel with an extensive multi-layered user space component that exposes functionalities to applications (apps) via Java Application Programming Interfaces (APIs). Although a core reference implementation of the OS is open

source and developed under a permissive license in the Android Open Source Project (AOSP), nearly all devices ship with heavily extended variants of the OS (so-called firmware) that include numerous proprietary system components. The security model of Android is mainly based on Linux process isolation and traditional POSIX permissions, with each application running as a separate user with minimal access to files outside its installation directory. Access to other resources (files and peripheral devices) is achieved via communication (IPC) with privileged system services that also run as separate processes. These userspace system services implement the logic of high-level Android Permissions (e.g. CAMERA, ACCESS_BACKGROUND_LOCATION). SLICEDROID builds on the fact that communication between processes and I/O operations must pass through the kernel and are therefore traceable in the kernel layer.

IPC in Android Android uses traditional Linux IPC mechanisms (UNIX sockets, pipes, etc.), in addition to a sophisticated message-passing IPC mechanism called binder, which facilitates remote procedure calls, and is implemented in the Linux kernel. In this paper, we are not interested in the internals of binder, rather we treat it as a message-passing mechanism where a process sends a message to another process and the latter receives it.

I/O in Android Android uses the Linux kernel with its Virtual File System (VFS)⁶ implementing a *Universal I/O Model* where userspace processes access all devices via standard system calls on files, mainly exposed in the `/dev` filesystem by `ueventd`.⁷ Opening a file of any type by pathname in Linux, creates a dedicated structure in the kernel that keeps track of information for that open file, and returns a file descriptor to userspace. This kernel structure also maintains information regarding how to handle operations performed on the file descriptor, e.g. `read/write`. Access to devices takes place via *universal* system calls on the file descriptors (`open`, `read`, `write`, `ioctl`, etc.).

System tracing in Linux The Linux kernel provides increasingly sophisticated and efficient ways to trace its execution, which are gaining popularity in many domains, including security monitoring. Notably, Linux offers mechanisms to hook onto its functions, namely `kprobes` and `tracepoints`. `Kprobes` are dynamic probes that allow hooking into function entry and exit points, while `tracepoints` are strategically defined

⁶<https://www.kernel.org/doc/html/v6.3/filesystems/vfs.html>

⁷<https://android.googlesource.com/platform/system/core/+master/init/README.ueventd.md>

static probes in the kernel. The main advantages of tracepoints are: (a) that they are considered a stable API (backward compatible), and (b) that they are usually strategically placed in the function body, allowing fine-grained access to the system state that may be difficult to attain using kprobes. Building on the probe points provided by the kernel and discussed above, higher level frameworks like *ftrace* [42], *perf*⁸ and *eBPF*⁹ allow tracing and instrumentation of the kernel. In particular, *ftrace* is a simple and powerful mechanism that is included in modern kernels and is exposed via their `tracefs` filesystem (usually mounted under `/sys/kernel/tracing`). *Ftrace* can be configured by echoing commands to special files of the `tracefs`, and is thus easy to deploy on different devices. We choose to use *ftrace* in our implementation and experiments, as it is the least complex—yet powerful enough—way to acquire the required traces. Naturally, *eBPF* can be used instead.

IV. APPROACH

In this section, we describe the basic elements of our approach: the problem definition, our IPC slicing method, its implementation on Android, and our data-driven mapping pipeline.

A. Problem definition

Although the problem of behavior reconstruction in Android has been studied implicitly in previous work, it has not been identified and studied independently. In this section we formally define the problem. Important to the definition of the problem are the following:

High-level behaviors: runtime characteristics of a program that are of interest to the analyst. High-level behaviors are formulated explicitly by the analyst in order to be useful in a given problem space, e.g. malware or intrusion detection. An example of a set of 14 interesting high-level behaviors (e.g. *Make Call*, *Access Location*, *Send SMS*) is given in Copperdroid [26] to be used for malware analysis. A program *exhibits* a high-level behavior b when its execution matches the mental model of the user for the given behavior, i.e. the behavior actually takes place.

Kernel-level events: units of information extracted from the running kernel of an operating system via a tracing mechanism. In related work, the main type of kernel-level events are system calls. Other kernel-level events (e.g. function entry/exit) can be defined and captured using suitable mechanisms.

Using the definitions above, we define two related problems:

Definition 1 (Membership Problem). Given as input a Behavior Set $B = \{b_1, \dots, b_n\}$, an Event Sequence $E = [e_1, \dots, e_m]$, and an index i ($1 \leq i \leq n$), return **1** if b_i was *exhibited* by the program, else return **0**.

Definition 2 (Sequencing Problem). Given as input a Behavior Set $B = \{b_1, \dots, b_n\}$, and an Event Sequence $E = [e_1, \dots, e_m]$, return a sequence of exhibited behaviors $S = [s_1, \dots, s_k]$, $s_i \in$

B , where for two behaviors s_i, s_j with $i < j$, either s_i was exhibited before s_j or s_i and s_j were exhibited at no particular order, i.e. the *happened before* relation can lead to a partial ordering of the exhibited behaviors.

While the Sequencing problem is strictly harder than the Membership problem, in many practical cases where individual high-level behaviors are defined as *point* behaviors (e.g. *start/stop phone call* vs *make a long phone call*), the problems can become equivalent. The Sequencing problem can be reduced to the Membership problem applied on successive time windows of an Event Sequence. We adopt such an approach in our mechanism, as we explain in the following sections.

Inherent constraints. For a behavior to be reconstructible from kernel-level events, it must perform at least one operation that crosses the process boundary and interacts with the OS kernel. This limitation may appear significant, however in general *interesting* high-level behaviors, especially the ones relevant for security and privacy, are *always* I/O behaviors [26], i.e. they involve data flow or access peripheral devices and thus need to interact with the OS kernel. We therefore limit our study to such I/O behaviors for the rest of the paper. In the following, we present our approach.

B. IPC slicing method

We base our approach on two key observations: (a) in Linux interaction with peripheral devices occurs via operations on virtual *device nodes* that drivers expose (usually in the `/dev` directory), and (b) information flow from devices to processes through the multiple layers of Android can be tracked by linking IPC information. For presentation purposes, we assume a simplified OS model that offers the operations `read` and `write` for I/O, and `IPC(dest)` for inter-process communication, in order to present the basic idea of our approach. All such events in the system are captured in a trace. We design two algorithms for identifying *process-level* information flows, a *forward* IPC slicing algorithm to capture `write` events associated with a given source process (t_{pid}) (Algorithm 1), and a complementary *backward* IPC slicing algorithm (presentation is omitted due to space limitations) to capture `read` events to a given destination (sink) process (t_{pid}).

Algorithm 1 Forward IPC Slicing

```

1: Input: events,  $t_{pid}$  ▷ List of events, target process
2: Initialization:
3:  $pid\_set \leftarrow \{t_{pid}\}$  ▷ set initially holds only target process
4:  $out\_events \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
5: for each event  $e \in events$  do
6:   Extract  $pid$  and type from  $e$ 
7:   if  $pid \in pid\_set$  then
8:     if  $e.type = IPC$  then
9:        $dest\_pid \leftarrow get\_destination\_pid(e)$ 
10:       $pid\_set \leftarrow pid\_set \cup \{dest\_pid\}$ 
11:     else if  $e.type = write$  then
12:        $out\_events \leftarrow out\_events \cup \{e\}$ 
13:     end if
14:   end if
15: end for
16: Return:  $out\_events$ 

```

⁸<https://perfwiki.github.io/main/>

⁹<https://man7.org/linux/man-pages/man2/bpf.2.html>

Algorithm 1 filters `write` events by sequentially going through the trace and adding `write` events to the output when the `pid` of the process associated with a given event is a member of the `pid_set`. This set initially contains the PIDs of processes under test; in the case of one process as presented in the algorithm, the set initially contains t_{pid} . A PID is added to the `pid_set` when there is an IPC path from a process already in the set towards this PID. The backwards slicing algorithm operates similarly, but on a *reversed* trace, filtering relevant `read` events.

An example of IPC slicing is shown in Figure 4 where the same event sequence is analyzed in the forward (left side) and backward (right side) directions with a target process P1. For the forward direction, the first two events are ignored as they originate from processes not in the `pid_set`. The third event P1: IPC(P2) adds P2 to the `pid_set`, which now consists of {P1,P2}. Event 4 of type `write` is picked and added to the output as it originates from a process (P2) in the `pid_set`. The next event is again skipped as it is a `read` event. The following event (P2: IPC(P3)) adds P3 to the `pid_set`, which now consists of {P1, P2, P3}. The next two events (7,8) do not change the state of the algorithm as event 7 is a `read` event and event 8 would add P1 to the `pid_set`, however P1 is already a member of this set. Finally event 9 is added to the output as it is a `write` event from a tracked process. This concludes the forward (*out-flows*) slicing. For the backward (*in-flows*) pass, we start from the end of the events list (event 9) and initialize the `pid_set` to contain only P1, the target process. Going backward, event 8 is an IPC event originating from P3 and received by a process in the `pid_set`; therefore the sending process is added to the `pid_set`. The algorithm continues so that after processing the last event in the backward pass (event 1), we have `pid_set`={P1, P2, P3} and the output consists of events {7,5,2}. We proceed to describe the realization of the described approach on Android.

Fig. 4. Examples of forward and backward slicing algorithm for $t_{pid}=P1$, the `pid_set` marked with `s` and the algorithms output list marked with `o`. Events included in the output are marked in gray and IPC events which affect the algorithm are marked in cyan.

C. Tracing kernel events in Android

In this section we show how we realized the scheme of Section IV-B on Android.

1) *Tracing machinery*: One of the fundamental challenges of implementing our approach on a real device is capturing kernel events of sufficient detail and quality with minimal overhead. Fortunately, the Linux kernel offers the tools (in terms of probes and tracepoints – see Section III) to achieve that. Contrary to other approaches that use eBPF to extract relevant events, e.g. IPCDump¹⁰ for Linux IPC, we opt to use the `ftrace` framework [42] to manage the Linux tracing tools. The advantage of this decision is simplicity and easy deployability.

Although traditional provenance tracking approaches focus on system calls, system call arguments do not carry sufficient information for detailed analysis. For example, resolving the endpoints of IPC (e.g. via binder) from system call arguments alone is generally impossible. Instead, modern tracing features of the Linux kernel allow on-demand instrumentation of appropriate functions, also supporting memory address dereferencing—thus allowing us to extract information from internal kernel structures. Below, we describe how we trace the operations corresponding to the abstract IPC, `read`, and `write` kernel events of Section IV-B.

2) *I/O tracing*: To capture I/O events, we focus on kernel functions that handle related system calls. The Linux Kernel’s *Virtual File System (VFS)* layer provides a uniform interface for the kernel to handle various I/O requests, including requests to device drivers. We trace the `vfs_read`, `vfs_write`, and `vfs_ioctl` functions. Tracing at the VFS layer allows us to access internal kernel structures. To uniquely identify the file to be written, we extract the 64-bit `i_ino` value, representing the inode number, and the 32-bit `i_irdev` value that is a combination of the major and minor number of a virtual device when the file is a special device file, else it is zero. We also extract the `s_dev` 32-bit value in `struct super_block`, which represents the major and minor number of the underlying device a filesystem resides in. In the case of a regular file, `i_irdev` will be zero and `s_dev` will correspond to the major/minor number of the device where the file is stored. In combination, these 3 fields can uniquely identify a file in Linux. To extract these fields, we attach a `kprobe` to the `vfs_write` function, follow the relevant pointers, and add appropriate offsets to dereference the specific fields. Our probes for `vfs_read` and `vfs_ioctl` are similar. We also trace TCP connection state transitions along with their associated IP addresses and protocol information via the `inet_sock_set_state` tracepoint. More extensive network tracing can be achieved by using other available tracepoints as appropriate, but falls outside the scope of this paper.

3) *IPC tracing*: Android/Linux uses classic IPC mechanisms prevalent in nearly all other Linux-based OSs, in addition to the binder mechanism, a sophisticated socket-like IPC mechanism. In our prototype, we choose to trace UNIX stream and datagram sockets, in addition to binder transactions. Although we do not trace other IPC mechanisms, most notably shared memory (e.g. *Android shared memory* or *dma buffers*), explicitly, we capture communication via these

¹⁰<https://github.com/guardicore/IPCDump>

mechanisms implicitly. This is because these shared memory designs rely on captured IPC mechanisms (UNIX sockets, binder) for bootstrapping and synchronization, e.g. to share file descriptors to the shared memory regions.

Tracing Binder The Linux kernel exposes static tracepoints that provide adequate information to trace binder send and receive events and link them together. We choose to trace the `binder_transaction` and `binder_transaction_received` tracepoints. The output format of these tracepoints includes a unique transaction identifier (`debug_id`) that can be used for linking.

Tracing UNIX stream sockets To trace UNIX stream socket communication, we attach kprobes to the `unix_stream_sendmsg` and `unix_stream_recvmsg` kernel functions.¹¹ Since UNIX stream sockets are a connection-oriented IPC mechanism, we can find the PID of the process at the other end of a socket by following fields of the `socket` structure, which is the first argument of both aforementioned functions.

Tracing UNIX datagram sockets Since UNIX datagram sockets are not connection-oriented, tracing the `unix_dgram_sendmsg` and `unix_dgram_recvmsg` kernel functions is not enough to link send and receive operations. We studied the implementation of `unix_dgram_sendmsg` and decided to hook `skb_queue_tail`, the specific function that is called by `unix_dgram_sendmsg` in order to add a message to the receiving socket’s receive queue. We traverse the kernel structures and extract the `inode` of the receiving socket which uniquely identifies a socket in the system.

4) *Slicing traces*: We instantiate the abstract algorithms of Section IV-B, based on the traced events described above. We consider the generic `vfs_ioctl` calls as both input and output events. We reconstruct IPC (`dest`) events by keeping a list of sending events (UNIX stream, datagram and binder) and matching them appropriately with receiving events. A significant challenge to our approach is *dependence explosion*, a well-known problem in provenance tracking [48]. Given a large time window, kernel events could be falsely attributed to processes that did not initiate them, leading to false positives. To address this challenge, we partition the traces in overlapping windows before processing them. The size of each window is a configurable value for the analyst to balance the trade-off of false positives and false negatives, as will become clear with our experiments later.

V. EVALUATION

We design an experiment to evaluate SLICEDROID’s core contributions, taking a conservative approach by only considering the device nodes present in SLICEDROID’s sliced output. We frame the problem as a binary classification one, where any given behavior either occurs or does not occur during an app’s execution. Since a ground truth dataset of mappings between kernel events and exhibited high-level behaviors does not exist, we create one by utilizing the semantic information carried by Android API method names, as explained later in

the section. Then, we proceed to investigate the following research questions:

RQ1: How to choose useful window size parameters?

RQ2: How effective is SLICEDROID on previously unseen applications?

RQ3: What is the tracing overhead of SLICEDROID?

A. Setup and data collection

In order to also capture API calls, used as ground truth, in a unified kernel trace, we adapt the setup of Nisi et al. [40]. Our approach parses Android’s Java source files and assigns two unique IDs to each API function it instruments, one for entry and one for return. Then, it inserts a write system call to the `/dev/null` device (captured by SLICEDROID through the `vfs_write` kernel event) at each function’s entry and return points, with a `count` argument equal to the API’s unique ID. In total, we instrument $\sim 120\,000$ methods of the Android Framework. Our analysis pipeline is shown in Figure 5.

Fig. 5. Empirical analysis pipeline

For our dataset, we randomly select 1 000 Android applications from the F-Droid¹² repository. Of these, we select applications that require at least one *dangerous* permission¹³, resulting in 798 distinct applications. We choose apps from F-Droid instead of the Google Play Store for two notable reasons: (a) F-Droid apps are open-source and can be assumed benign—this is important for our ground truth construction approach, and (b) most F-Droid apps do not require to register an account, and are thus amenable to automated testing. We run and trace these applications on a Pixel 9 device with Android 15 AOSP. Similarly to Nisi et al. [40], we use the *UI/Application Exerciser Monkey*¹⁴ tool to inject events into applications to trigger different behaviors. Although the *Monkey* tool has well-known limitations, it is a suitable choice for our experiments since, (a) achieving high-coverage for individual apps is not a goal, (b) other specialized approaches perform only marginally better [53]. For each app, we inject 1 000 input events at an interval of 500 ms and capture the

¹²<https://f-droid.org/>

¹³<https://developer.android.com/guide/topics/permissions/overview>

¹⁴<https://developer.android.com/studio/test/other-testing-tools/monkey>

¹¹https://elixir.bootlin.com/linux/v6.1.121/source/net/unix/af_unix.c#L2972

trace. Half of the traces form the *Analysis set*, while the other half form the *Evaluation set*, used only in Section V-D. In total, traces number almost 2 billion events, including more than 12 million VFS operations on special files.

B. Constructing ground truth labels

To construct ground truth labels, we use Android API method names as ground-truth proxies. For our experiments, we focus on five sensitive I/O behaviors that manifest themselves deep in the Android framework shown in Table II. Such behaviors are the most difficult to reconstruct as they involve IPC through multiple layers of Android with different mechanisms (binder, sockets, dma). Other behaviors that manifest themselves with accesses to specific device nodes (e.g. SMS, Telephony) or regular files (e.g. Contacts, Photos, Messages) can be added to our implementation in a similar manner. First, we group device nodes which appear in the *Analysis set* and assign a high-level behavior description to each group based on information exposed by the kernel and manual analysis of the *Analysis set*. The mapping of device nodes to high-level behaviors is summarized in Table II.

TABLE II
MAPPING OF DEVICE NODES TO HIGH-LEVEL BEHAVIORS

Behavior	Device nodes
Use camera (Camera)	lwis-*
Record audio (Audio in)	pcmC0D8c
Use bluetooth (Bluetooth)	ttySAC18
Use NFC (NFC)	st21nfc
Access location (GPS)	gnss_dump, gnss_ipc

Then, we construct ground truth labels as follows. If an application calls an API that is semantically related to a behavior (*API called*) and our approach captures application access to a device node associated with the behavior (*Behavior identified*, see Table II), this is considered a True Positive. If a device node for a given behavior is captured but no characteristic API was invoked, this is a False Positive. Other results are defined accordingly, as shown in Table III. Table IV provides an example of the mappings between behaviors and their characteristic APIs. Although best-effort, our approximation of the ground truth adequately serves the purpose of empirically validating the feasibility and added value of SLICEDROID.

TABLE III
GROUND TRUTH LABELS

Result	Behavior identified	API called
True Positive	✓	✓
False Positive	✓	✗
True Negative	✗	✗
False Negative	✗	✓

C. RQ1: Tuning the window size

A small window size could result in missed behaviors as the IPC chains connecting an application to a device access may be broken up; a large window size, on the other hand, may lead to false positives, as behaviors initiated by other applications and system processes could introduce noise. In

TABLE IV
ILLUSTRATIVE EXAMPLE OF BEHAVIORS WITH THEIR CHARACTERISTIC APIs.

Behavior	APIs
Camera	...camera2.impl.CameraDeviceImp.execute
	...camera2.CaptureResult.CaptureResult
	hardware.Camera.handleMessage
...	
Audio in	media.AudioRecord.stop
	media.AudioRecord.startRecording
Bluetooth	bluetooth.BluetoothDevice.writeToParcel
	bluetooth.le.ScanResult.createFromParcel
	bluetooth.le.ScanRecord.parseFromBytes
...	
NFC	nfc.NfcActivityManager.onActivityPaused
	nfc.NfcActivityManager.onActivityResumed
	nfc.NfcAdapter.getContext
...	
GPS	location.LocationManager.onNmeaReceived
	location.LocationManager.getListener

order to empirically test the effect of the window size, we run experiments using the first half of our dataset (*Analysis Set*) consisting of traces generated by 399 applications. The performance of our approach with different window sizes is depicted in the ROC curve of Figure 6. We observe that the ability of the slicing approach to capture behaviors varies with window size. As expected, when using a small window size (<100 events), accesses to device nodes are missed, and therefore the True Positive Rate (TPR) suffers. As the window size increases, more relevant events are captured and associated with the application under test, and thus the TPR increases at the cost of False Positives. Starting at a window size of around 500 events, all behaviors are captured and larger window sizes do not bring any benefit.

RQ1: The window size can be tuned to trade off precision for recall. The optimal window size for capturing all behaviors is between 200 and 500 events.

Fig. 6. The ROC curve of the tuning dataset with different window sizes of X events each, $X \in [25, 50, 100, 200, 500, 1000, 2000, 5000, 10000, 20000, 50000, 100000]$.

D. RQ2: Effectiveness evaluation

To evaluate the effectiveness of our approach on unseen applications, we repeat the experiment from the previous section on the *Evaluation Set (eval1)* of 399 unseen applications (second half of the dataset as depicted in Figure 5). We compare SLICEDROID with two baselines:

- *OwnEvents*: Only consider events originating from the target process. Representative of existing system call analysis techniques.
- *AllEvents*: Consider all events in the trace without slicing. Used to evaluate the added benefit of our window-based slicing approach.

TABLE V

EVALUATION RESULTS ON UNSEEN APPLICATIONS. BASELINES IN GREY.

Baselines/window	TP	FP	TN	FN	PR	RE	F1
<i>OwnEvents</i>	0	0	1504	21	0	0	–
<i>AllEvents</i>	20	128	1376	1	13.5	95.2	23.7
25	12	1	1503	9	92.3	57.1	70.6
50	17	7	1497	4	70.8	81.0	75.6
100	17	13	1491	4	56.7	81.0	66.7
200	20	25	1479	1	44.4	95.2	60.6
500	20	50	1454	1	28.6	95.2	44.0
1000	20	70	1434	1	22.2	95.2	36.0
2000	20	87	1417	1	18.7	95.2	31.3
5000	20	95	1409	1	17.4	95.2	29.4

Our results for the two baselines and SLICEDROID with several window sizes are presented in Table V. We observe that SLICEDROID significantly outperforms the two baselines for all examined window sizes. Regarding the baselines, *OwnEvents* fails to capture any behavior since all studied behaviors involve IPC. *AllEvents* assumes that all events in the trace are associated to the target process, and thus captures all behaviors. However, since it does not perform slicing to verify that data flow exists, it incurs a high false positive rate with a resulting F1 score of 23.7%. SLICEDROID significantly outperforms the baselines on the examined window sizes with a maximum F1 score of 75.6% for a window size of 50 events. Starting from a window size of 200 (F1 = 60.6%), the only false negative observed was attributed to an `AudioRecord.stop` API call with no matching `AudioRecord.startRecording` call in the trace, suggesting that an audio recording did *not* take place. Therefore, SLICEDROID captured *all* behaviors (100% Recall).

From the results, it is also apparent that SLICEDROID is not perfect, incurring a considerable number of false positives. False positives can be attributed to several factors: (a) noise from other applications or background processes on the device that the Exerciser Monkey might have interacted with, and which SLICEDROID attributed to the application under test, (b) missing APIs in the ground truth, and (c) alternative calling methods, e.g. `Intents`.¹⁵ In any case, all positive instances identify potential information flow between the application under test and device nodes associated with the selected behaviors. As we observed in our case studies presented in following section, noise caused by sporadic false positives is acceptable in practice.

Detailed per category results for window sizes of 200 and 500 events, are summarized in Table VI. We see that SLICEDROID with a window size of 200 events, achieves an F1 score of 60.6% when considering all five behaviors, with a recall of 95.2% and a precision of 44.4%. The false positive associated with the camera originates from the trace of the

TABLE VI

EVALUATION RESULTS ON UNSEEN APPLICATIONS PER BEHAVIOR

Behavior	window size = 200						
	TP	FP	TN	FN	PR	RE	F1
Camera	10	1	294	0	90.9	100	95.2
Audio in	2	0	302	1	100	66.7	80.0
Bluetooth	5	11	289	0	31.3	100	47.6
NFC	0	6	299	0	0	0	–
GPS	3	7	295	0	30.0	100	46.2
Total	20	25	1479	1	44.4	95.2	60.6

Behavior	window size = 500						
	TP	FP	TN	FN	PR	RE	F1
Camera	10	1	294	0	90.9	100	95.2
Audio in	2	1	301	1	66.7	66.7	66.7
Bluetooth	5	21	279	0	19.2	100	32.2
NFC	0	20	285	0	0	0	–
GPS	3	7	295	0	30.0	100	46.2
Total	20	50	1454	1	28.6	95.2	44.0

Flashy app,¹⁶ a simple flashlight app that uses the flash hardware of the camera. Indeed, the only device node in the sliced trace for this app suggesting camera usage behavior is `lwis-flash-lm3644`, a device node related to the camera’s flash hardware. Therefore, the observed behavior is in line with the advertised use of the app. To further evaluate our tool, we test it on another dataset (*eval2*) of 1000 randomly re-sampled F-Droid applications. The results for both datasets are summarized in the ROC curves of Figure 7. The similarity of the curves increases our confidence in our key insights, summarized below.

Fig. 7. The ROC curve of testing on two datasets with different window sizes ranging from 25 events to 100k events.

RQ2: SLICEDROID is effective in reconstructing high-level behaviors, being able to identify *all* studied behaviors for window sizes greater than 200 events. To achieve this efficiently and transparently, SLICEDROID trades off precision.

E. RQ3: Tracing overhead evaluation

We employ the popular benchmarking tools `Geekbench`¹⁷ (CPU benchmark) and `AnTuTu`¹⁸ (composite benchmark), similar to other works in the domain [54], [55]. We also run

¹⁶<https://f-droid.org/packages/rocks.poopjournal.flashy/>¹⁷<https://www.geekbench.com/>¹⁸<https://www.antutu.com/en/index.htm>¹⁵<https://developer.android.com/guide/components/intents-common>

stress tests using `sysbench`¹⁹ to measure File I/O speed. AnTuTu and Geekbench output performance scores (the higher the better), while `sysbench` outputs transfer speed in MB/s (the higher the better). We run each benchmark 5 times and report the mean performance values with and without tracing. A summary of the results for all benchmarks is presented in Table VII, showing that SLICEDROID incurs negligible overhead under realistic workloads.

TABLE VII
TRACING OVERHEAD ON MULTIPLE BENCHMARKS \pm MAX/MIN

Benchmark	Native	w/Tracing	Overhead
AnTuTu v10	1182627 \pm 100k	1229396 \pm 110k	–
Geekbench 6 single	1740 \pm 35	1726 \pm 18	<1%
Geekbench 6 multi	4532 \pm 45	4529 \pm 45	<0.1%
Sysbench File I/O	42 \pm 4 MB/s	39 \pm 2 MB/s	7%

RQ3: SLICEDROID incurs minimal tracing overhead (<1%) on standard popular benchmarks.

VI. CASE STUDIES

To test the practical usefulness of SLICEDROID, we perform case studies on real-world applications.

Commercial spyware. We select the Mobile-Tracker²⁰ app from the study of Liu et al. [56] for its powerful capabilities (e.g. covert camera and microphone recording by abusing Android permissions) in its free version. We perform a series of experiments on a Google Pixel 9 device with a stock Google image of Android 15, manually exercising the spyware’s capabilities while recording kernel traces with SLICEDROID. A graphical representation of the resulting behavioral profiles is presented in Figure 8. Such depictions relay useful information to users and analysts while enabling further processing (e.g. ML-based anomaly detection). The *resolution* of the behavioral profile can be configured by the window size parameter; a larger window size potentially means capturing more behaviors (also increasing false positives), while a smaller window size results in more windows, potentially missing some behaviors due to broken IPC chains, but conveying richer ordering information and reducing false positives.

Figure 8a depicts the behavior of the Mobile-Tracker app when a login is made to the web interface controlling the app and a remote request to capture a picture from the device’s camera is sent. We observe TCP connections established to a remote server (IP of a cloud provider in the Netherlands) and access to the GPS hardware. Indeed, the location of a device is fetched automatically when a user logs into the web interface. We then see numerous camera-related events followed by a new connection establishment to the remote server. The screen is off during the test, showing no signs of camera usage, while the captured photograph is made available for download through the web interface. Figure 8b shows the behavior of a remote request to fetch the location of the device. As expected, the trace includes access to the GPS hardware. Figure 8c shows the behavior of a remote request

(a) Login and remote picture: a cluster of TCP and GPS related events around window 40 (login in web interface), followed by camera-related ones, followed by TCP events (data transmission)

(b) Remote location request: A GPS event followed by a TCP connection to 51.158.154.183.

(c) Remote audio recording (1 minute): Distinct recording start and stop events and TCP connection to 51.158.154.183.

(d) 1 hour idle operation: No suspect behaviors noted.

Fig. 8. Behavioral profiles of Mobile-Tracker under different scenarios (window size: 500 events, overlap: 100). Behaviors depicted with different symbols on different rows. A green upward-pointing arrow depicts TCP connection establishment; an orange downward-pointing one, connection termination.

to capture microphone audio. Audio input behaviors, marking the beginning and end of the recording, are reconstructed and shown in the behavioral diagram, followed by a connection to the remote server. Finally, Figure 8d shows a 1-hour-long trace where the device is idle and the commercial spyware app runs in the background. We see no signs of secondary malicious behavior, but observe connections to Google servers that the app uses for command and control.

Facebook and TikTok. We downloaded and created new accounts for the popular *TikTok* and *Facebook* apps from the Google Play Store. In the generated behavioral profile, we observed a potential privacy issue. Both apps receive status updates when the camera of the device starts being used by another application and when it stops (and therefore becomes available again), even when they do not have the CAMERA permission (in the case of TikTok). The core of the issue lies in the Android framework’s implementation of camera status callbacks, e.g. the `CameraManager.AvailabilityCa`

¹⁹<https://github.com/akopytov/sysbench>

²⁰<https://mobile-tracker-free.com/>

llback²¹ that can be registered even when applications do not possess the CAMERA permission, as we verified with a custom application. Such issues leak device state information, which malicious apps could exploit, e.g. to launch phishing attacks [57], [58]. We reported this issue to Google and they confirmed that the current design allows applications to register camera status callbacks without a permission, since such functionality may be needed in order to use the flashlight²². Whether or not this design choice constitutes a privacy issue is open to discussion.

Case studies takeaways.

- SLICEDROID is useful in uncovering covert behaviors in commercial spyware apps.
- SLICEDROID is useful in identifying unexpected behaviors in Android OS components.

VII. DISCUSSION

Threat model and trust: Contrary to previous approaches for Android application analysis, our middleware-agnostic approach does not trust the middleware (Android userspace) to be correct. Therefore, as shown in the case study of Section VI, it can be used to discover bugs, e.g. missing permission checks in the Android framework. The rate of vulnerability disclosures for the system and framework layers of Android has increased in recent years and kernel-level behavioral analysis can be used to find such bugs during testing, or even identify threats originating from the exploitation of such vulnerabilities in the wild. In general, kernel-level tracing can offer increased transparency to the inner workings of the extensive Android userspace. However, it still trusts the monolithic Linux kernel, which contains multiple, potentially faulty, proprietary drivers. Furthermore, sophisticated attacks that leverage kernel vulnerabilities to elevate their privileges can attempt to hide themselves from the tracing mechanism. Additional hardware-based protection measures [32], [59] can help mitigate such risks. Regarding evasion, SLICEDROID’s simple design, relying only on IPC and file accesses to reconstruct *all* potential behaviors, is inherently resilient to malicious applications injecting noise in the traces to evade detection, especially compared to approaches that rely on API method tracing or pattern matching. Accounting for sophisticated collusion attacks [60] can be achieved by associating the generated behavioral profiles via the already-available IPC information.

Conceptual limitations. Noise: Due to the black-box nature of IPC slicing, it is possible for event sequences generated by one process to be falsely attributed to another process. The existence of central IPC hubs like the `servicemanager` process can aggravate this effect. While such noise is unavoidable, its effect is mitigated when studying the behavioral profile of an application over a large-enough period of time (see Figure 8). SLICEDROID also facilitates further investigation of suspicious

behaviors by providing the IPC chains to the analyst. **Behavior granularity:** SLICEDROID captures behaviors at a coarse device granularity, similar to previous works on malware detection [26]. More detailed behaviors, corresponding to specific API calls can be learned from the patterns of device node accesses captured by SLICEDROID, potentially utilizing machine learning approaches. Such approaches should be designed with caution to limit evasion opportunities.

Implementation limitations. Behavior number: In our prototype implementation, we trace five interesting and challenging to capture behaviors, to evaluate the capabilities of SLICEDROID. More behaviors can be added in a similar manner. To get an estimate of the effort required to add new behaviors to the system, it took three junior software engineers, previously unrelated to the project, one person-month in total to add the capabilities to reconstruct the SMS, call logs, contacts, and calendar access behaviors. Adding more behaviors will not have an effect on the effectiveness and performance of SLICEDROID as measured in this paper, since new behaviors correspond to new source/sink files (device nodes or regular files) that do not interfere with those studied in this paper. **Requires root:** Although `ftrace` is extensively utilized by higher-level Android tools for performance tracing (`atrace`, `systrace`, `Perfetto`), access to some required functionalities exposed in the `tracefs` (e.g. defining `kprobe` events) is restricted for unprivileged processes. Therefore, we had to root the device used for our implementation. Android vendors and legislators should consider permitting access to more features of the Linux tracing infrastructure by default to increase transparency and user control. **Disk footprint:** The tracing format of `ftrace` contains a lot of redundant information, e.g. a trace of a Monkey run on a single app (1 000 input events) can be around 500 MB in size, while its compressed version will be around 30 MB. Adapting an eBPF-based solution like `eAudit` [61] to Android could further reduce the disk footprint and the overall overhead.

Other Threats to validity. Construct – Experimental setup: Our approach to acquire ground truth data on the behaviors that actually took place on the device was to exercise open-source (benign) applications and map high-level API calls that they perform to behaviors. We believe that this is a sufficiently accurate approximation of the ground truth for our experiments. **External – Generalization:** SLICEDROID’s approach can be adapted to profile and verify application behavior on any Android device and any OS with a Linux kernel, including devices other than smartphones. The prerequisites for this is access to the tracing filesystem, kernel symbols, and mappings of device nodes to behaviors. The latter can be obtained either by following our approach of instrumenting the OS (which requires modifications) in an initial learning phase, or by developing an app that performs known behavior sequences and tracing its execution.

Practical implications. Kernel tracing for transparency: On modern mobile devices, the TCB, from a user-centric viewpoint, consists not only of the kernel and drivers, but also of a significantly larger proprietary middleware stack, including the Android framework and various privileged pre-

²¹<https://developer.android.com/reference/android/hardware/camera2/CameraManager.AvailabilityCallback>

²²<https://issuetracker.google.com/issues/406667208>

installed applications. Kernel-level behavioral analysis can be used to detect security and privacy issues in these components, complementing static and traffic analysis techniques used in previous studies [10]. **Real-time dynamic analysis and forensics:** Our techniques can be used as a building block for real-time protection measures to combat threats such as colluding apps, dynamic code loading, or the exploitation of vulnerabilities in the Android framework. Furthermore, the same techniques can be used for forensic analysis, e.g. to detect increasingly evasive mercenary spyware [62]. **Improving existing approaches:** There exist numerous proposals for system-call based Android malware detection in the literature. Notably, Crowdroid [52] proposes crowdsourcing application behaviors (via system calls) from real user devices. Our findings suggest that our techniques can significantly improve the effectiveness of these approaches. In general, instead of relying only on the system calls of the process under test, analysis should consider all system events associated with the process via slicing.

Future work. Although SLICEDROID contributes a step towards resolving the long-standing research problem of mapping kernel traces to Android APIs, further progress is required. In particular, data-driven approaches (e.g. using machine learning) could be employed to learn such mappings. However, care has to be taken to avoid overfitting to specific device models or OS versions and enabling evasion attacks.

Conclusion. Overcoming limitations that have previously led to negative results, we showed that it is possible to reconstruct high-level informational behaviors of any Android process efficiently and transparently, at the cost of a configurable decrease in precision. We also showed that such approaches can be used in practice to construct behavioral profiles of applications on user devices to identify suspicious and unexpected behaviors. Our techniques can be used to improve existing Android security tools and as a basis for new ones.

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